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Pedagogical Strategies, Approaches and Methodologies to Support Disciplinary Literacy at Primary and Post-Primary Levels

A Review of the Literature

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Summary of Findings: Pedagogical Strategies, Approaches and Methodologies to Support Disciplinary Literacy at Primary and Post-Primary Level

Disciplinary literacy is the focus of growing attention in the research literature at both primary and post-primary level (Shanahan & Shanahan, 2008). Integrated literacy and content area instruction has the potential to enhance literacy skills (e.g. vocabulary, comprehension, writing proficiency) while concurrently developing content area knowledge throughout the school system (Guthrie et al., 2004; Cervetti et al., 2006). The findings from the literature challenge the separation of literacy from content area instruction and suggest a shift towards the full integration of both in the school curriculum (Hwang et al., 2021).

Disciplinary literacy involves “knowledge of and skill with the specialised linguistic codes, technical vocabularies, and discourse practices that draw from and reproduce the epistemic understandings and routine practices of a discipline” (Moje, 2015, p. 257). In schools, teachers can support students to gain insights into how questions are asked and answered within the discipline, how conclusions are drawn, supported, contested and defended (Goldman et al., 2016; Shanahan & Shanahan, 2017). Instruction is tailored to the specific features and demands of each discipline. Students are better able to build knowledge and form sophisticated models, ideas and discourses in text as they apprentice themselves into disciplinary expertise. This focus on disciplinary knowledge construction provides students with meaningful opportunities to apply higher order thinking skills and critically analyse texts. These capacities are crucial for life both in- and out-of-school.

Reading informational texts in content areas like science, mathematics, geography, and history presents challenges to the reader as they grapple with different text genres, text structures, organisational features, and typographical cues (Cervetti & Pearson, 2018). Vocabulary is more demanding and linguistic and grammatical features add to the complexity. Knowledge demands are higher on the reader and such texts often require a level of background or prior knowledge. Therefore, the literature has increasingly focused on the integration of discipline-specific literacy teaching by both generalist teachers (at primary level) and specialist teachers (at post-primary level).

Research suggests that students taught using project-based methods exhibited greater gains in content knowledge, had higher levels of engagement, and had more positive perceptions of subject content than their traditionally taught peers (Holm, 2011; Balemen & Keskin, 2018; Duke et al., 2021). Teachers need supportive school structures including resources and time to plan and enact inquiry units, and a strong base for disciplinary teaching and inquiry or project-based approaches (Hasni et al., 2016; Kalinowski et al., 2019; Scott et al., 2018).

The available evidence indicates that there are substantial benefits to be gained from integrating writing with learning in different subjects at both primary and post-primary level (Graham et al., 2020). This writing can take a number of different forms and modalities, depending on subject-specific demands (Shanahan & Shanahan, 2008; Graham et al., 2020). It should be supported by the associated reading of appropriate discipline-specific texts in a critical manner, the linkage of writing with subject-based inquiry and the teaching of appropriate strategies to support the planning, drafting and revision of text (Ockenburg et al., 2019; Weiss et al., 2021; Wissinger and Ciullo; 2018). This form of writing provides opportunities for students to engage critically with sources and to craft and hone their own thinking.

Key Recommendations

Pillar 2 Improving teachers' and Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) practitioners' professional practice

- Supporting the integration of literacy with various disciplines is challenging at both primary and post-primary level; Professional Development (PD) in this area is a complex endeavour. Studies of PD note success is achieved with supportive school structures, collaborative approaches among teachers that include observation of practice, the provision of appropriate supporting materials and resources for teachers, and time to plan amongst other factors (Hasni et al., 2016; Kalinowski et al., 2019; Scott et al., 2018).

Pillar 4 Improving the curriculum and the learning experience

- The findings from the literature challenge the separation of literacy from content area instruction (Guo et al. 2016; Hwang et al. 2021). This suggests that a shift towards the full integration of both in school curricula is warranted. This recommendation should be considered in light of the ongoing review of the curriculum at primary and post-primary level.
- Teachers should support students to gain insights into how questions are asked and answered within each discipline, how conclusions are drawn, supported, contested and defended. Instruction should be tailored to the specific features and demands of each discipline (Goldman et al., 2016; Shanahan & Shanahan, 2017; Wright et al., 2016).
- Students taught using project based methods exhibit greater gains in content knowledge, have higher levels of engagement, and have more positive perceptions of subject content than their traditionally taught peers (Baleman & Keskin, 2018; Holm, 2011). Inquiry based or project based methodologies that link content-area learning with literacy should be considered in both primary and post- primary curricula. It is important to draw on the characteristics of successful approaches as outlined in the report (e.g. the need for teacher instruction on *how* to successfully research and analyse sources for a project).
- Meaningfully integrating writing with learning in a given discipline has a substantial impact on both writing skills and conceptual learning (Graham et al., 2020). Curriculum reform at both primary and post-primary level should outline clear expectations for how writing (in various forms and modes) is used to support and advance subject-based learning. This focus on disciplinary knowledge construction provides students with meaningful opportunities to apply higher order thinking skills and critically analyse texts. These capacities are crucial for life both in- and out-of-school.
- Writing should be taught in a manner that supports the characteristic ways of thinking and teaching associated with different subjects, with increasing specialisation as learners progress into post-primary school (Graham et al., 2020; Miller et al., 2018; Shanahan & Shanahan, 2008).
- Intrinsic links should be forged between the critical reading and analysis of multiple sources and the writing of synthesis texts based on these sources, in line with subject-specific expectations (Van Ockenburg et al., 2019). This form of writing provides opportunities for students to engage critically with sources and to craft and hone their own thinking.
- The integration of writing with disciplinary learning demands that teachers are familiar with key writing approaches and pedagogies (e.g. the teaching of *planning* as part of

the writing process; how to use sources); this extends to teachers of content-areas at post-primary level (Graham et al., 2020; Van Ockenburg et al., 2019).

Disciplinary Literacy

Definitions of Disciplinary Literacy

Disciplinary literacy refers to the various forms of reading, writing and oral language that support thinking and learning across the curriculum (Shanahan & Shanahan, 2008). While the literature in this area refers to *disciplines*, these can be considered as being broadly analogous to the *subjects* that constitute the school curriculum in Ireland (e.g. geography, science). Key to the concept of disciplinary literacy is the idea that each discipline has its own characteristic forms of knowledge construction that influence the forms of communication considered legitimate or correct therein (Goldman et al., 2016). For example, the way in which a scientist critically evaluates a text may be markedly different to the type of analysis undertaken by a historian, musician or artist (Shanahan, Shanahan & Misichia, 2014). The expansion in how we conceptualise idiosyncratic forms of literacy has led to a concomitant expansion in how we *define* literacy. For example, Draper and Siebert (2010, p.30) define literacy as the ability to “negotiate (e.g., read, view, listen, taste, smell, critique) and create (e.g., write, produce, sing, act, speak) texts in discipline-appropriate ways or in ways that other the discipline (e.g., mathematicians, members of historians, artists) would recognize as ‘correct’ or ‘viable’”. This discipline-specific focus is also captured in the definition offered by the International Literacy Association, which refers to literacy as: “The ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, compute, and communicate using visual, audible, and digital materials *across disciplines* and in any context” (emphasis added). This broad conceptualisation of literacy is important if the teaching of literacy is to be meaningfully aligned with the wide array of values, dispositions and knowledge associated with different curriculum subjects.

Disciplinary Literacy: Reading across the Curriculum

There is broad consensus in the literature that the ability to use strategies to engage with a range of genres, texts and text types is central to effective literacy development (Cervetti & Pearson, 2018). Reading informational texts in content areas like science, mathematics, geography, and history presents challenges to the reader as they grapple with different text genres (such as, persuasive, procedural, explanation, report), text structures (such as, cause and effect, compare and contrast, proposition and support, problem/solution), organisational features and typographical cues (such as, table of contents, index, bold face or italic font). Vocabulary is more demanding and linguistic and grammatical features add to the complexity. Knowledge demands are higher on the reader and such texts often require a level of background or prior knowledge. In addition, information is presented in multiple ways and modes (e.g. graphs, diagrams, photographs, and maps).

Content area literacies

In a synthesis and critique of the pedagogical recommendations to develop content area literacies with adolescents Fang (2012) identifies four approaches: cognitive, socio-cultural, linguistic and critical. Each of these approaches draw on different theoretical paradigms and different teaching approaches.

The cognitive approach involves systematic, explicit, multiple strategy instruction for reading and writing in the content areas. Such strategies include, predicting, inferencing, monitoring, summarising, concept mapping and note taking. The sociocultural approach draws on the extent to which readers are able to construct meaning drawing not only on background knowledge but also on factors such as, purpose, interest, motivation and identity. The out-of-school literacies that, for example, adolescents bring to the classroom are both a bridge and

resource for developing content area literacies. The linguistic approach recognises that content area texts are written in language that differ significantly from those that constitute everyday texts. Students must learn to cope with language patterns, sentence complexity and grammatical structures of such texts in order to construct knowledge in various disciplines. Finally, the critical approach views all texts as inherently ideological or value laden depending on the intent of the author and the socio-political-historical contexts of its production. Content area texts are “positioned and positioning” (Janks, 2005, cited in Fang, 2012). This approach has a strong social justice agenda. Fang (2012) notes that these approaches are not mutually exclusive and, indeed, it is the synergy and complementarity of the approaches that allow teachers to tailor their instruction towards curricular goals, to the needs of students, and to learning outcomes for specific tasks.

The integration of literacy and content area instruction

Hwang et al. (2021) investigated whether integrated literacy and content area instruction in science and social studies would enhance vocabulary and comprehension. Usefully, they define integrated instruction between literacy and content areas as instruction in which “literacy activities (reading and/or writing) serve as a tool to cultivate content knowledge” while concurrently “content teaching serves as a lever to facilitate literacy skills (vocabulary and/or comprehension” (p.2). Integrated literacy and content area instruction can provide motivating contexts for students to engage in reading and writing. Models such as the Concept Oriented Reading Instruction model (CORI) (Guthrie et al., 2004) and Seeds of Science/Roots of Reading (Cervetti et al. 2006) have consistently shown growth for reading comprehension, vocabulary and content area knowledge while concurrently building motivation and engagement. Results from the Hwang et al., (2021) meta-analysis of (quasi)experimental studies revealed significant effect sizes (ES) for both vocabulary (ES=0.91) and comprehension (ES=0.40) and content area knowledge (ES=0.89). Positive

effect sizes (Hedges' $g=0.66$) were also determined in a meta-analysis of seven studies conducted by Guo et al. (2016) on the effects of integrated literacy and science content on vocabulary outcomes in pre-kindergarten and kindergarten children. This suggests that integrated literacy and content area instruction has the potential to enhance literacy skills in vocabulary and comprehension while concurrently developing content area knowledge throughout the school system. The findings from Hwang et al. (2021) and Guo et al. (2016) challenge the separation of literacy from content area instruction and suggest a shift towards the full integration of both in the school curriculum.

Content area reading strategies versus disciplinary literacy strategies

The literature distinguishes between content area reading strategies and disciplinary literacy strategies. Typically, content area reading strategies involve the use of graphic organisers such as, KWL and concept mapping charts or study skills strategies such as, notetaking to enhance summarisation. Content area reading strategies “can serve as entry ways into disciplinary literacy practices” (Shanahan & Shanahan, 2017, p. 285). However, this “one-size-fits all” approach (Moje, 2015), which involves the instruction of literacy strategies common in multiple contexts, is insufficient unless it is tailored to the specific features and demands of each discipline. In a study conducted by Shanahan and Shanahan (2008) disciplinary experts approached texts differently and leveraged different reading strategies to privilege certain kinds of information. Over the past decade there has been a shift from content-area literacy skills to disciplinary literacy, focussing on the skills required for reading and writing in a specific field, such as science (Wright et al., 2016).

Disciplinary literacy involves “knowledge of and skill with the specialised linguistic codes, technical vocabularies, and discourse practices that draw from and reproduce the epistemic understandings and routine practices of a discipline” (Moje, 2015, p. 257). Disciplines such as, history, geography, social studies, science and literature have negotiated

norms and conventions, written discourse practices in how to create, disseminate and evaluate knowledge, specialised language conventions, and unique forms of academic language that shape knowledge claims and argumentation within each disciplinary community (Goldman et al., 2016; Shanahan & Shanahan, 2017). Disciplinary literacy involves communities of practice and cultures in which certain kinds of texts are read and written for certain purposes and with and for certain audiences (Moje, 2015).

In schools, teachers can support students to gain insights into how questions are asked and answered within the discipline, how conclusions are drawn, supported, contested and defended. Instruction is tailored to the specific features and demands of each discipline. Students are better able to build knowledge and form sophisticated models, ideas and discourses in text as they apprentice themselves into disciplinary expertise (Shanahan & Shanahan, 2017). As such, the development of disciplinary literacy in classrooms is a spiralling, developmental apprenticeship process that leads, over time, to rich learning.

Traditional versus inquiry-based approaches

Much of the research on the integration of literacy with subject-area teaching has emphasised the potential of carefully executed inquiry-based approaches that balance teacher input with student-driven learning. In a systematic review conducted by Khalaf and Mohammed Zin (2018) distinctions are made between traditional and inquiry-based pedagogies. The authors observe that traditional models are underpinned by behaviourist theories whereas inquiry-based learning models are underpinned by constructivist theories. The authors identify challenges in both approaches. The challenge for traditional learning models, they note, is the dominant authority of the teacher in the classroom, the focus on teacher-centred rather than student-centred learning, and the limited development of knowledge, skills, competencies and performance accompanied by minimal educational outcomes. Inquiry based approaches are underpinned by collaborative and communicative processes as a means of

constructing knowledge. Challenges to this approach are identified in the review. These include current school systems including fixed curricula, timetables and assessments; the role of the teacher as a facilitator; teacher beliefs and attitudes; the student knowledge of the inquiry process; and the lack of professional development (PD) for teachers. In a review of research from 2000-2011 conducted by Holm (2011) students taught using project based methods exhibited greater gains in content knowledge, had higher levels of engagement, and had more positive perceptions of subject content than their traditionally taught peers.

The characteristics of inquiry or project based approaches

Furtak et al. (2012) observe a variability in how inquiry based or project based approaches are defined. Nevertheless, the models of instruction identified in the systematic reviews and meta-analyses undertaken for this report share a number of characteristics and conceptual understandings.

These include:

- Theoretical perspectives, originating from the work of authors like Dewey and Kilpatrick (Hasni et al., 2016), which are anchored in constructivist or socio-constructivist perspectives. Teachers' knowledge of the theories underpinning instructional practices impact implementation. Theories should be made more explicit by researchers (Wright et al., 2016) to ensure a strengthening of the connection between theory and practice underpinned by joint efforts of researchers and teachers (Yang et al., 2020).
- Pedagogical approaches that promote learning which enable students to create links between school and life, support life-long learning, and encourage self-controlled learning (Balemen & Keskin, 2018).
- Real world inquiries that are rooted in authentic scientific problems or questions which are relevant to the students. Curiosity and creativity are nurtured (Hasni et al., 2016).

- Teachers as facilitators, providing scaffolding, guidance and strategic instruction (Holm, 2011).
- Students are engaged in investigations or design activities and develop a final product or artefact. Students encounter the central concepts and principles of the disciplines studied (Hasni et al., 2016).
- Communities of practice involving students, teachers and others in a community of inquiry as they collaborate about a problem (Moje, 2015).
- Promotion of higher cognitive skills, including both divergent and convergent thinking skills, problem solving and metacognition. Students develop interpersonal skills, self-disciplines and responsibility while working with others (Hasni et al., 2016).
- The models impact, in a positive way, on the emotional and cognitive development of students thereby increasing motivation and engagement (Goldman et al., 2016).
- Some of the models emphasise the affordances of digital technologies for accessing information or exploring phenomena or worlds beyond the classroom walls through for example, augmented reality (Pedaste et al., 2020).

A review of 48 studies (Balemen & Keskin, 2018) found a large effect size ($d=1.063$) in favour of project based learning (PBL) when compared to traditional approaches in the context of academic performance in the sciences. PBL affects students' academic performance in a positive way and was 86% more effective compared with traditional approaches. There were no statistically significant differences between the average effect sizes depending on different education levels (i.e. primary, secondary or tertiary). PBL has a high effect value whether used on its own or in combination with other techniques. In a meta-analysis of experimental and quasi-experimental studies Furtak et al.(2012) found that inquiry based approaches were effective in general with an overall mean effect size (ES) of 0.50. Moreover, when these approaches were coupled with teacher-led activities the ES was approximately 0.40 higher than

those with student-led conditions. Although not a meta-analysis or systematic review, the Duke et al. (2021) large scale study, of project based learning approaches in social studies, in low socio-economic school districts, showed a significant effect size (ES) for social studies (ES=0.482) and information reading (ES= 0.182) in favour of the experimental group over the comparison group. Interestingly, the result for information writing (ES=-0.047) and student motivation (ES=0.193) showed that the intervention did not have a statistically significant effect on either. The authors observe that the degree of consistency between fidelity of implementation of curriculum materials and the project based lesson units was associated with both higher year end achievement in informational writing and associated positive change in student motivation.

Professional development for preservice and in-service teachers

The complexity of implementing these approaches should not be understated. The approaches often require multiple and fundamental shifts in classroom practices but also changes at system and school level to optimise outcomes. Teachers need supportive school structures including resources and time to plan and enact inquiry units, and a strong “knowledge in practice” base for disciplinary teaching (Moje, 2015) and inquiry or project based approaches (Holm, 2011).

Lesley (2014) identified three key issues in initial teacher preparation for content literacy instruction: (1) greater cohesion in definitions of content area literacy, (2) a clearer understanding of how to prepare pre-service teachers to offer instruction in disciplinary literacies and (3) methods to overcome the dispositional barriers of pre-service teachers toward implementing content area literacy. In a systematic review of 29 studies conducted in the USA, spanning over 50 years of research, Scott et al. (2018) revealed three overarching categories emerging regarding perceptions, resistance, and experience of pre-service teachers in teaching literacy across the disciplines. First, they note that teacher candidate beliefs and perceptions

are strongly impacted by the instructional content and literacy-focused methods courses. Positive beliefs do not always transfer back to implementation in the classroom. Second, pre-service teachers lack the generative knowledge and skills and are resistant to integrate instruction when they only receive short courses in literacy. Third, the systematic review reported positive growth for pre-service teachers in terms of gaining experience, diversifying strategy instruction, connecting learning to practice, gaining a deeper knowledge of content instruction and pedagogy when embedding content-area instruction within field based school placements.

In a systematic review of 38 articles, Kalinowski and colleagues (2019) identified the features associated with PD to promote academic language in different subjects. Though the authors are not conclusive about the elements of PD which are most effective, their review provides an illustration of the many potential avenues for supporting teachers in this endeavour. The features of PD included cooperation and collaboration between teachers; the provision of materials/resources to support teachers in implementing new approaches and the application of learning from PD sessions in classrooms, associated review of student work and teacher observation.

Hasni et al. (2016) call for a commitment to Professional Development (PD) for both preservice or inservice teachers to enable teachers to enact project based or inquiry based approaches, to acquire the knowledge to do so, to develop collaboration skills among teachers using these approaches, and to develop a positive self-concept and attitude towards these approaches with teachers.

It is unsurprising that equipping teachers with the knowledge and skills needed for teaching literacy in the disciplines is a complex endeavour.

Disciplinary Literacy: Writing across the Curriculum

Writing is a core feature of communication, thinking and action in most disciplines. The available evidence suggests that the integration of writing and content-area learning is beneficial for the development of both writing skills and conceptual knowledge in a given subject.

Writing to learn across disciplines

One of the most substantial reviews undertaken in this area involved a meta-analysis of 56 experimental and quasi-experimental studies on how writing was used to support learning in science, social studies and mathematics (Graham et al., 2020). Writing to learn can be defined as “the use of writing as a vehicle for strengthening, extending, and deepening students’ knowledge” (Graham et al., 2020, p. 180). Empirical work on the integration on writing to learn is informed by two main theoretical perspectives: cognitive and socio-cultural (Graham et al., 2020). Cognitive perspectives emphasise the goal-directed, strategic decision-making that is required to take newly learned information and convey it through a new mode and in one’s own words. Socio-cultural theories, on the other hand, emphasise the way in which writing is used to communicate newly learned information to other members of a community. The headline effect size of 0.30 across the studies indicated a generally positive impact of the integration of writing and content area instruction, with the authors indicating both can be “profitably integrated” (p. 218). This positive effect was found across the grade levels and subjects included in the study (Grades 1-12). As part of the review, the authors coded each study according to a range of moderating identifiers, such as the forms of writing undertaken by students, the nature of the professional development received by teachers and the duration of the writing activities. From an instructional perspective, the authors distinguished between writing to *record information* which involved relatively low levels of knowledge

transformation (e.g. taking notes on new content as it is encountered) and *analysis and interpretation*, which involved deeper processing or transforming this knowledge into a new form (e.g. marshalling new learning to write an argument based on the topic). The authors considered a variety of different writing activities, such as writing summaries of information, writing arguments drawing on new information, writing narratives in the form of stories or poems and writing that was primarily graphical in form (e.g. mind maps). It was notable that, despite finding an overall positive effect size, their analysis did not reveal a strong pattern indicating which forms of writing were most likely to contribute to effective writing to learn. This being said, Graham and colleagues advise that teachers must exercise discretion in carefully matching writing activities with teaching and learning activities, as not all writing activities will be effective in all contexts. The findings of this meta-analysis are supported by a smaller scale review of 17 qualitative and quantitative writing to learn studies conducted by Chmarkh (2021).

Linking writing with discipline-specific ways of thinking

As noted in the section on disciplinary reading, a core tenet of disciplinary literacy is that the form of literacy activities undertaken will vary according to the distinctive epistemological, linguistic and socio-cultural norms within a discipline (Shanahan & Shanahan, 2008). As disciplinary literacy is a relatively new construct in the literature, much of the research in this area is still at the level of single studies, many of which are small in scale and unamenable to systematic review. However, a number of reviews captured by the current review of reviews illustrate the distinctive ways in which writing can be integrated with different subjects. For instance, Weiss and colleagues (2021) reviewed the instructional features most commonly associated with immersive argument-based inquiry, a form of writing instruction that emphasises the *process* of argumentation within *inquiry* based approaches. This form of writing instruction emphasises the importance of student involvement in question

setting, small group work and discussion, first-hand investigation and the communication of scientific norms by the teacher (amongst other features) as a driver for genuine engagement with argumentative writing. While Weiss and colleagues focused on argumentation as a vehicle for scientific literacy, Huerta and Graza's (2019) review focused on the development of *academic language* in science. Their synthesis of 29 qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods studies further underscored that writing to learn in science can support language and conceptual development for both ELL and non-ELL students. Turning to a different discipline, in a review of historical disciplinary literacy for students with learning disabilities, Wissinger and Ciullo (2018) and report on 12 quantitative studies with moderate to large effect sizes. Instruction in historical writing demanded different forms of knowledge evaluation, for example the use of the STOP mnemonic used in one of the studies reviewed (De La Paz, 2005): Suspend judgment, Take a side, Organise ideas, Plan more as you write. Though the reviews cited here are relatively narrow in the curricular breadth, they provide further illustration of how writing and content area instruction can be fruitfully integrated for diverse learners.

The integration of writing with post-primary subjects can provide a demanding task. Miller and colleagues (2018) provide an extensive review of 43 quantitative, qualitative and mixed method studies across disciplines in grades 6 to 12. Their review underscores a number of important pedagogical features of successful literacy integration at this level, organised under three main themes:

1. *Context (how writing tasks are implemented)*

Successful studies on secondary literacy integration regularly draw on the use of templates to support pre-writing. Instruction involved a number of explicit teaching approaches, including self-regulated strategy development (e.g. Harris & Graham, 1999) and subject-based inquiry approaches.

2. *Cognition (how thinking is demonstrated in writing tasks)*

Teachers have an important role to play in linking writing with the metacognition in subject-based learning (e.g. writing journal entries on new learning). The studies reviewed also provided evidence for the strong reciprocal link between writing and reasoning in oral language.

3. *Content (how discipline-specific concepts/ knowledge are realised in writing)*

The review indicated, like others cited here (e.g. Graham et al., 2020) that writing generally had a beneficial impact on learning concepts associated with a discipline and their engagement with issues relating to the discipline. Miller and colleagues finish their review with the following conclusion (p. 115): “when thoughtfully planned within an instructional setting that encourages cognitive acts, content-area writing tasks positively impact a variety of students’ learning outcomes, across both disciplines and different types of learners.”

Linking source analysis and synthesis with writing

One of the key features of writing in many disciplines is the ability to synthesise information from multiple sources and subsequently re-form this knowledge to construct a coherent and accurate text. Looking across several disciplines at post-primary level, Van Ockenburg and colleagues (2019) provide a review of what they term ‘synthesis texts’, that is, texts which involve writing about information gleaned from the reading of a variety of sources. Their review underscores the importance of explicitly teaching each of the processes involved in *selecting*, *organising* and *connecting information* from across sources. For example, to *select information*, students must be taught to fully comprehend individual sources and engage in activities that encourage evaluation of these sources (e.g. through questioning, comparing/contrasting sources, examining source information). To *organise information*,

students should learn how to compare source features by, for example, examining authorial information; they should also learn how to analyse source content, by for example comparing information from sources using graphic organisers. To *connect information*, students should be taught how to write coherent texts based on the selection and organisation of information, through, for example, comparing and contrasting the organisation of sample/mentor texts.

Limitations in the available evidence

Cautious interpretation of the studies included in this review is warranted for a number of reasons. Firstly, it is evident that experimental studies, and consequently, reviews of such studies, have tended to focus on how disciplinary literacy supports a relatively narrow range of subjects. Many of the studies underpinning these reviews were conducted in the United States, which has a distinctive curriculum structure that varies from that of Ireland. Limited evidence fell within the scope of this review on how writing supports subjects like visual art at primary level or engineering at post-primary level. It should also be noted that, compared to other areas of literacy, there are comparatively fewer meta-analytic and systematic reviews available for disciplinary literacy. Secondly, much of the writing reported in these reviews aligned mostly with ‘traditional’ pen and paper forms. For example, Graham et al.’s (2020) meta-analysis included only three studies involving digital forms of writing. Thirdly, some of the review studies included in this report are descriptive rather than evaluative or conclusive in nature. Fourthly, though this report addresses disciplinary literacy across school sectors, it is self-evident that the nature and content of literacy instruction for the disciplines at primary level will be different to that expected at post-primary level.

Notwithstanding these cautionary notes, the available literature provides clear evidence for the double advantage of integrating literacy instruction with subject-based learning; both *literacy achievement* and *conceptual understanding of the subject* benefit.

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Biographies

Dr Bernadette Dwyer is an Associate Professor in the school of Language, Literacy and Early Childhood Education where she lectures and researches in the area of Literacy. She has published refereed articles in high ranking journals, chapters in books, commissioned reports, and has edited conference proceedings. Her most recent book publication is *Using technology to improve reading and learning*. Bernadette is a regular presenter at both national and international conferences and has given a range of invited keynote addresses at conferences around the world. Bernadette has been awarded a number of awards including the DCU President's award for Engagement in the Community (2016) and the Technology in Reading Research Award (2017) by the TILE-SIG of the International Literacy Association. Bernadette served on the International Literacy Association (ILA) board from 2013-2016 and was elected as President of ILA 2018. She chaired the International Taskforce on the systematic review of the literature pertaining to *Children's Rights to Read*. and *Children's Rights to Excellent Literacy Instruction*. Bernadette is currently engaged in research in the areas of multimodal/ digital literacies; inquiry-based learning; and disciplinary literacies.

Patrick Burke is an Assistant Professor in the School of Language, Literacy and Early Childhood Education at DCU. Prior to joining the faculty at DCU, Patrick worked in a variety of roles: as a primary school teacher, as an International Fellow in the Children's Literature Centre at Frostburg State University (MD, USA), as an advisor with the Professional Development Service for Teachers, and as a Lecturer in Education at Mary Immaculate College, Limerick. Patrick has contributed to the drafting of the Primary Language Curriculum (2019) as a member of the NCCA Primary Language Development Group and is a current executive committee member of the Literacy Association of Ireland. His teaching and scholarly work has been recognised by several organisations including the National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning and the International Literacy Association. Patrick is currently completing doctoral studies on teachers' disciplinary literacy practice at primary and post-primary level.

Dr Eithne Kennedy is an Associate Professor in the School of Language, Literacy and Early Childhood Education, DCU Institute of Education. She is the Programme Chair of the Master of Education in Literacy Professional Practice and teaches on a range of literacy modules at undergraduate level. She is the recipient of the International Literacy Association's Outstanding Dissertation Award (2010) for her doctoral thesis: *Improving literacy achievement in a disadvantaged primary school: Empowering classroom teachers through professional development*. As director of the *Write to Read* research initiative, she collaborates with schools in disadvantaged areas to create powerful literacy environments that motivate and engage children as readers, writers and thinkers. She is one of the lead authors of NCCA desktop reviews of research on literacy education in the context of the redevelopment of the primary language curriculum (2012, 2019) and served on the NCCA Curriculum Development Group (2012-2015). She is a member of the Federation of European Literacy Associations special interest group: *The Initial Teaching of Literacy Across Europe*. She has served as one of the Irish partners on the European Commission's ELINET research consortium on literacy policy and practice and the *European Cooperation in Science and Technology Project* which investigated the digital and multimodal practices of young children (birth to age 8).

Disciplinary literacy: Reading and Writing Across the Curriculum

Title of Article and Authors, Year of Publication	Number of studies reviewed in article/kind of review	Effect sizes (If available)	Foci of Article	Age range / Grade Level(s)	Findings (also refer to definitions of literacy/numeracy, as used in article/report)
Balemen, N., & Keskin, M. Ö. (2018). The Effectiveness of Project-Based Learning on Science Education: A Meta-Analysis Search. <i>International Online Journal of Education and Teaching</i> , 5(4), 849–865.	48 studies	$d=1.063$ large effect size			Meta-analysis of the effectiveness of Project Based Learning (PBL) in the context of academic performance in the sciences. PBL is 86% more effective in science education compared to traditional approaches. PBL promotes learning enabling students to create links between school and life, supports life-long learning, and encourages ‘self-controlled learning’ Analysis of studies conducted at primary, secondary and tertiary educations suggested no statistically significant differences between the average effect sizes depending on different education levels. In sum, PBL affects students’ academic performance in a positive way. PBL has a high effect value whether used on its own or in combination with other techniques.PBL yield positive results at all levels of teh school system.
Chmarkh, M. (2021). “Writing to Learn” Research: A Synthesis of Empirical Studies (2004-2019). <i>European Journal of Educational Research</i> , 10(1), 85–96.	17 papers; published 2004-2020 Includes both qualitative and quantitative studies	Not available	Writing to learn in L2 settings	This is not elucidated but reference is made to college-level students in the body of the paper	The author is critical of an over-emphasis on learning to write in second languages and over-emphasis on cognitive aspects of writing. The paper emphasises, in particular, the distinction between writing to learn in assessment/graded and ungraded settings; distinguishes between what McDermott (2010) calls writing to earn and writing to learn assignments. The author draws on “inductive content analysis” in synthesising studies.The findings arranged according to four research questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1. What are the effects of writing when used as a learning tool? Author concludes based on studies reviewed that writing to learn has beneficial impact on content area learning

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 2. Is there a difference in the effectiveness of writing to learn activities across various disciplines and grade levels? No notable differences noted. ● 3. What variables might maximize or mitigate the learning potential of writing? See table 2 in the document. ● 4. What are students and teachers' perceptions of writing to learn strategies/tasks? Generally positive views reported.
Fang, Z.. (2012). Approaches to Developing Content Area Literacies: A Synthesis and a Critique. <i>Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy</i> , 56(2), 103–108.	Synthesis and critique	N/A	Approaches to developing content area literacies	Adolescent	<p>Author espouses that efforts to develop content area literacies with adolescents must recognise the strengths and limitations of each of four approaches. Each of these approaches draw on different theoretical and empirical traditions and teaching practices.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Cognitive approach: systematic, explicit teaching of strategies, mental routines, and procedures for reading and writing in content areas. Such strategies include, predicting, inferencing, monitoring, summarising , concept mapping and note taking. Multiple strategy instruction is recommended. 2. The Sociocultural approach : The extent to which readers are able to construct meaning draws not only on background knowledge but also on factors such as, purpose, interest, motivation and identity. The out-of-school literacies that adolescents bring to the classroom are both a bridge and resource for promoting content area literacies. 3. The Linguistic Approach: Content area texts are written in language that differ significantly from those that constitute everyday texts. Students must learn to cope with language patterns, sentence complexity and grammatical structures of such texts in order to construct knowledge in various disciplines. Instruction should not consist of drill-like exercise devoid of functionalities or content contexts. 4. The critical approach: All texts are inherently ideological or value laden depending on the intent of the author and the socio-political-historical contexts of its production. Content area texts

					are “positioned and positioning” (Janks,2005). This approach has a strong social justice agenda.
Furtak, E. M., Seidel, T., Iverson, H., & Briggs, D. C. (2012). Experimental and Quasi-Experimental Studies of Inquiry-Based Science Teaching: A Meta-Analysis. <i>Review of Educational Research</i> , 82(3),300–329. https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654312457206	37 experimental studies conducted between 1996-2006	Mean effect size overall of 0.50	Inquiry based learning in Science	k-12	Meta-analysis exploring the effect of inquiry-based teaching on student learning in Science Studies that contrasted epistemic activities (students' knowledge of how scientific knowledge is generated) or combination of procedural epistemic and social activities had the highest mean effect sizes (ES=.50). In addition,teacher-led activities had a mean effect size of 0.40 larger than those with students led activities.
Goldman, S. R., Britt, M. A., Brown, W., Cribb, G., George, M., Greenleaf, C., Lee, C. D., & Shanahan, C. (2016a). Disciplinary Literacies and Learning to Read for Understanding: A Conceptual Framework for Disciplinary Literacy. <i>Educational Psychologist</i> , 51(2), 219–246.					Across the disciplines of literature, science, and history teams of researchers conducted a conceptual meta-analysis. For each discipline, a team of researchers, teachers, and specialists in that discipline engaged in conceptual meta-analysis of theory and research on the reading, reasoning, and inquiry practices exhibited by disciplinary experts as contrasted with novices.The clusters for each discipline were grouped into 5 higher order categories of core constructs: (a) epistemology; (b) inquiry practices/strategies of reasoning; (c) overarching concepts, themes, and frameworks; (d) forms of information representation/types of texts; and (e) discourse and language structures. It is clear from the Project READI framework developed from this review that the knowledge, skills, practices, and processes that are articulated in the core constructs and learning goals of each of the disciplines develop through an iterative process of introducing and then iteratively deepening them. These iterations need to occur over multiple years of instruction.

<p>Graham, S., Kihara, S. A., & MacKay, M. (2020). The Effects of Writing on Learning in Science, Social Studies, and Mathematics: A Meta-Analysis. <i>Review of Educational Research</i>, 90(2), 179–226. https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320914744</p>	<p>56 experiments or quasi-experiments from 53 documents/papers</p>	<p>0.30</p>	<p>Focus on writing to learn in science, social studies, mathematics; writing included many forms (e.g. summarising; arguments; note taking; graphic organisers and mindmaps - see page 194); included both digital and handwritten forms of writing</p>	<p>Grades 1-12 (Grades 1-11 in actual studies included)</p>	<p>Writing to learn is defined as “the use of writing as a vehicle for strengthening, extending, and deepening students’ knowledge (cf. Graham & Perin, 2007)” (p.180). Studies captured in the review included integration of writing with science, mathematics, social studies and a roughly equal balance of elementary, middle and high school populations. Various forms of writing were captured in the meta-analysis, including informational, journal, argument and narrative writing, as well as more graphical forms. Writing improved content area learning; “statistically significant average weighted ES of 0.30” (p.206). The effect was similar across each of the disciplines included; no content area differences noted. Writing about content improved writing at all grade/age levels, more or less equally. All types of writing had statistically significant effect sizes. The authors conclude that writing about science, social studies and mathematics enhanced learning (however, 18% of studies did show a negative effect with no clear explanation for why identifiable. The authors suggest it may be due to poorly constructed or applied writing activities.). None of the moderators identified by the authors (E.g. grade level, content area, PD received by teachers, type of writing, length of time writing) accounted for why some writing to learn studies were more successful than others. The following observations for practice made: writing supports learning across grades and should therefore be used across grades; multiple forms of writing can be used to improve content area learning; writing to learn can be “profitably integrated” into science, social studies and mathematics; this integration of writing to learn and content is not universally effective - some features of the integration require scrutiny; teachers must “carefully match” writing tasks with goals for content area learning; not all approaches that are effective in studies will be so in each classroom; very few (3) studies involved digital writing tools; further comparison research studies are needed.</p>
<p>Guo, Y., Wang, S., Hall, A. H., Breit-Smith, A., & Busch, J. (2016). The Effects of Science Instruction on Young Children’s Vocabulary Learning: A Research</p>	<p>7 studies</p>	<p>Mean effect size 0.66</p>	<p>effects of science instruction on young children’s vocabulary learning</p>	<p>preschool and kindergarten</p>	<p>Science instruction studies with preschool and kindergarten children to explore the impact of science instruction on young children’s vocabulary outcomes. Science instruction examined using science intervention and vocabulary intervention (focus on science vocabulary) Mean effect size of 0.66 suggests that increased focus on science impacted vocabulary development ,especially with domain specific words.</p>

<p>Synthesis. <i>Early Childhood Education Journal</i>, 44(4), 359–367. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-015-0721-6</p>					
<p>Hasni, A., Bousadra, F., Belletête, V., Benabdallah, A., Nicole, M.-C., & Dumais, N. (2016). Trends in Research on Project-Based Science and Technology Teaching and Learning at K-12 Levels: A Systematic Review. <i>Studies in Science Education</i>, 52(2), 199–231.</p>	<p>48 articles published between 2000 and 2014</p>				<p>Project-based teaching originates from the work of authors like Dewey and Kilpatrick and is anchored in constructivist or socio-constructivist perspectives. The Systematic review investigated features used to define project-based science and technology teaching (PBSTL); the justification for using this approach; and interventions illustrating PBSTL.</p> <p>Concepts and features underpinning PBSTL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Authentic scientific problem or question anchored in real world inquiries. ● Students are engaged in investigations or design activities ● Students develop a final product or artefact ● Involve students ,teachers and others in a community of inquiry as they collaborate about a problem ● Promotes students’ use of cognitive tools. <p>Justification of PBSTL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PBSTL promotes the acquisition of Science and Technology skills and competencies, such as, scientific inquiry skills, technological skills, design process and problem solving skills. ● PBSTL promotes higher cognitive skills, including both divergent and convergent thinking skills, problem solving and metacognition. Students develop interpersonal skills, self-disciplines and responsibility while working with others. ● PBSTL encourages curiosity and creative abilities among students. Learning is anchored in real world inquiries or issues allowing students to formulate investigation questions that are relevant to them. ● PBSTL has a positive impact on the emotional and cognitive development of students and increases motivation and engagement. <p>Professional Development :Preservice or inservice teachers’ commitment to PBSTL training or to using this approach in their</p>

					teaching practices had a positive impact on: (a) teachers enacting this approach; (b) the acquisition of S&T knowledge; (c) the development of collaboration skills; and d) self-concept and attitude towards S&T
Holm, M. (2011). Project-based instruction: A review of the literature on effectiveness in prekindergarten through 12 th grade classrooms. <i>River Academic Journal</i> ,7(2)	17 studies conducted between 200-2011		project-based learning	k-12	In a review of research conducted from 2000-2011 students taught using project based methods exhibited greater gains in content knowledge, had higher levels of engagement, and had more positive perceptions of subject content than their traditionally taught peers. Research clearly indicates project-based learning is beneficial with positive outcomes including increases in levels of student engagement ;heightened interest in content; more robust problem-solving capabilities and greater transfer of skills to new situations. Practical difficulties in implementing Project based learning in schools are noted.
Huerta, M., & Graza, T. (2019). Writing in Science: Why, How, and for Whom? A Systematic Literature Review of 20 Years of Intervention Research (1996–2016). <i>Educational Psychology Review</i> , 31(3), 533–570. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09477-1	29 articles included in final analysis; included qual/quant/mixed methods; published between 1996-2016;	Overall effect size not provided	Particular focus on ELLs in science writing studies and how they compare to non-ELL samples	K-12 settings	Literacy is used as a term but not defined; focus is on academic language which is defined by the authors as “language possessing distinctive features such as technical vocabulary and discourse patterns not present in the everyday language learners use apart from academic settings” p. 554). Early qualitative studies confirm that writing <i>does</i> improve scientific understanding; later quantitative studies provide further evidence (compared to control groups); this holds for ELL and non-ELL populations. Writing-to-learn in science classrooms can improve both conceptual understanding and academic language; i.e. attention to literacy boosts rather than detracts from science learning. Culturally and linguistically responsive teaching is important; home languages and cultures should be a springboard for science/literacy learning. Quality of teaching is crucial; simply writing about science is not sufficient. Non-ELL studies focused on science writing that involved a process approach, including modelling, feedback and revision. Important that a dual focus on scientific concepts and language development is common for both ELL and non-ELL populations; this has not been the case in all research captured in this review
Hwang, H., Cabell, S. Q., & Joyner, R. E. (2021). Effects of Integrated Literacy and Content-area Instruction on	35 quasi-experimental studies	vocabulary Effect size (ES) 0.91 Comprehension ES 0.40			Meta-analysis of the effects of integrated literacy and content-area instruction (Science and Social studies)on vocabulary and comprehension outcomes in K-5. Results positive and significant for vocabulary and comprehension. Further an effect size was observed for

<p>Vocabulary and Comprehension in the Elementary Years: A Meta-analysis. <i>Scientific Studies of Reading</i>, 0(0), 1–27. https://doi.org/10.1080/10888438.2021.1954005</p>		<p>C Standardised comprehension on outcomes (ES=0.25) Content knowledge (ES=0.89)</p>			<p>standardised comprehension outcomes (ES=0.25) but not for standardised vocabulary outcomes. Overall results of Meta-Analysis indicate that integrated content-area instruction has the potential to enhance vocabulary and comprehension while simultaneously benefiting science and social studies knowledge. Definition: “<i>integrated instruction</i> between literacy and the content areas as instruction in which literacy activities (reading and/or writing) serve as a tool to cultivate content knowledge (science and/or social studies) while, at the same time, content teaching serves as a lever to facilitate literacy skills (vocabulary and/or comprehension).”</p>
<p>Kalinowski, E., Gronostaj, A., & Vock, M. (2019). Effective Professional Development for Teachers to Foster Students’ Academic Language Proficiency Across the Curriculum: A Systematic Review. <i>AERA Open</i>, 5(1), 2332858419828691. https://doi.org/10.1177/2332858419828691</p>	<p>38 articles; published between 2000 and 2016; all but one study from the US; included qual/quant/mixed method studies</p>	<p>Not provided</p>	<p>Focus on PD to promote academic language in different subjects;</p>	<p>Teachers in K-12 settings (‘general education’ settings)</p>	<p>The authors do not define literacy; focuses on academic language drawing on Schleppegrell’s definition (“the language used in schooling for purposes of learning” (Schleppegrell, 2009, p. 3). All studies included reported some level of positive results from the PD provided. Studies varied from 3 months, to one school year, to more than three years. Most involved a variety of PD format including workshops, coaching, professional learning communities. Most had expert involvement (language/literacy/content area). In most studies, PD was adapted to teacher needs and feedback and in some studies incentives (e.g. time-off; PD credit) were provided.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Content-focus of PD: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Research/theory-based approaches: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Involved scaffolding (e.g. of words/phrases) ■ Sheltered instruction ■ Inquiry-based learning ○ Application oriented knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Knowledge was made relevant to classroom practice in all studies ○ Home languages/cultures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Using and valuing home language/cultures present in most studies ○ Focus on student learning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ e.g. a focus on potential difficulties students might encounter; language acquisition; assessment of learning ● Didactic features of PD:

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cooperation and collaboration (e.g. sharing progress/experiences) ○ Input, application, and reflection: Often involved presentations/ readings. Analysis of recorded teaching in some studies. ○ Active learning: e.g. apply learning from PD sessions; discussing/analysing student work; observation of teaching ○ Materials for language support: Most studies included exemplar materials for teachers to use. <p>Authors cannot be conclusive about which elements in the studies are most effective; the study provides a <i>description</i> of the features most commonly found in PD.</p>
Khalaf, B. K., & Mohammed Zin, Z. B. (2018). Traditional and Inquiry-Based Learning Pedagogy: A Systematic Critical Review. <i>International Journal of Instruction</i> , 11(4), 545–564	43 studies conducted between 2002-2017		Traditional Versus inquiry-based learning pedagogies		Systematic review of traditional and inquiry based learning models. It identifies the advantages and disadvantages of both learning methods. Traditional models are underpinned by behaviourist theories where the dominant authority in the classroom is the teacher. The main drawbacks for traditional learning models is the limited development of knowledge, skills, competencies and performance accompanied by minimal outcomes. Inquiry-based learning is underpinned by cognitive constructivist theoretical perspectives. With inquiry-based teaching students are engaged in problem solving in a collaborative learning environment. Drawbacks of inquiry-based approaches are raised by the authors. These include current school systems including fixed timetables and assessments; the role of the teacher as a facilitator; teacher beliefs and attitudes; student knowledge of the inquiry process; and lack of PD for teachers
Lesley, M. K. (2014). Policy, Pedagogy, and Research: Three Issues Affecting Content Area Literacy Courses for Secondary-Level Teacher Candidates. <i>Literacy Research & Instruction</i> , 53(1), 50–71.	Not a systematic review				Through a review of literature pertaining to instruction in content area literacy published primarily during the past two decades emerged three key issues that need to be addressed in order to bring about maximum benefits for teacher candidates in this course: (1) greater cohesion in definitions of content area literacy, (2) a clearer understanding of how to prepare teacher candidates to offer instruction in disciplinary literacies and (3) methods to overcome the dispositional barriers of teacher candidates toward implementing content area literacy.

https://doi.org/10.1080/19388071.2013.826761					
<p>Miller, D. M., McTigue, E. M., & Scott, C. E. (2015). The Quality of Recent Studies in Content-Area Writing in Secondary Classrooms. <i>Literacy Research: Theory, Method, and Practice</i>, 64(1), 461–477. ERIC.</p>					<p>This is a methodologically-focussed paper that reviews the same studies as Miller et al. (2018) be;pw; its pertinent findings for the current study are captured in the next row.</p>
<p>Miller, D. M., Scott, C. E., & McTigue, E. M. (2018). Writing in the Secondary-Level Disciplines: a Systematic Review of Context, Cognition, and Content. <i>Educational Psychology Review</i>, 30(1), 83–120. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-016-9393-z</p>	<p>43 studies included in final analysis; Between 2000 and 2013, subsequently updated to 2016; includes quan/qual/mixed method studies;</p>	<p>Not provided</p>	<p>Approaches to writing captured under content-area, disciplinary and adolescent literacy, but deliberately omitting new and visual literacies; focus on more ‘conventional’ forms of writing;</p>	<p>Secondary learners grade 6-12</p>	<p>The authors refer to several definitions of literacy including that of ILA and NCTE; specifically delineates content area, disciplinary and adolescent literacies; define writing as follows: “the concept of writing was operationalized through the qualities of completeness and coherence” (p.87). Findings organised according to three main themes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Context (how writing task was taught/implemented) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Templates/models for pre-writing were very common; both conceptual knowledge and writing (argumentation) saw improvements from their use ○ Instructional delivery: typically involved explicit strategy instruction (e.g. SRSD); others were based on the philosophy of the discipline; both were successful in improving writing/content outcomes. ○ Other findings: variation in writing task can prove fruitful (doesn’t just have to be traditional essays); planning/revising strategies improve writing; more frequent writing more likely to be successful ○ Summary: pre-writing/planning tasks are valuable; strategy instruction and discipline-based inquiry models can improve writing; logistics of how writing is implemented is important (e.g. frequency of lessons) ○ Cognition (how thinking is realised/demonstrated in writing tasks)

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Metacognition: teachers have important role to play in supporting metacognition (e.g. through specific prompting; keeping a journal of metacognitive strategies used; varying the text to suit different audiences) ○ Reciprocal relationship between writing (e.g. arguments) and oral argumentation ○ Conclude that writing in content areas supports metacognitive acts relevant to the content area and thus overall learning in the area ○ Content (discipline specific learning) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Studies measuring achievement found that focussing on writing improved disciplinary learning ○ Using more extended writing as formative assessment improved learning in the discipline and performance on assessments <p>The authors conclude: “In total, teachers and researchers can, with a great measure of certainty, draw the following conclusion: when thoughtfully planned within an instructional setting that encourages cognitive acts, content-area writing tasks positively impact a variety of students’ learning outcomes, across both disciplines and different types of learners.” (p.115)</p>
Pedaste, M., Mitt, G., & Jürivete, T. (2020). What Is the Effect of Using Mobile Augmented Reality in K12 Inquiry-Based Learning? <i>Education Sciences</i> , 10(4), 94. https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10040094	15 articles			k-12	<p>Augmented reality (AR) combines the real and the virtual worlds. A systematic review of the potential of implementing augmented reality (AR) in inquiry-based learning was conducted. The findings reveal that AR, in the context of inquiry-based learning, is mostly implemented successfully to achieve cognitive and, less often, motivational and emotional learning goals. The AR solutions have mainly been applied in the Conceptualization phase and less in the Investigation phase of an inquiry-based learning unit. The authors note the importance of AR in all phases of Inquiry based learning. For example, in the orientation phase to immerse students in situations where the problem occurs or in the Discussion phase to encourage collaboration among students. Most of the studies confirmed the positive effect of AR scenarios on cognitive, motivation, emotional outcomes for students</p>
Scott, C. E., McTigue, E. M., Miller, D. M., &	29 studies conducted in USA			Pre-service teachers	Systematic review of 50 years of research regarding teacher preparation in literacy across the disciplines. Three overarching categories emerged

<p>Washburn, E. K. (2018). The what, when, and how of preservice teachers and literacy across the disciplines: A systematic literature review of nearly 50 years of research. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i>, 73, 1–13. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.03.010</p>	<p>and published between 1969-2017</p>				<p>regarding perceptions, resistance and experience of pre-service teachers when they received instruction in these areas through coursework and practicums. Perceptions: Pre-service teachers' beliefs and perceptions are strongly impacted by the instructional content- and literacy-focussed methods courses. Resistance: Positive beliefs do not always transfer back to implementation in the classroom. Pre-service teachers lack the generative knowledge and skills to integrate instruction when they only receive short courses in literacy. Experiences: Researchers reported positive growth for pre-service teachers in terms of gaining experience, diversifying strategy instruction, connecting learning to practice , gaining a deeper knowledge of content instruction and pedagogy when embedding content-area instruction within field based practicums.</p>
<p>Van Ockenburg, L., Van Weijen, D., & Rijlaarsdam, G. (2019). Learning to write synthesis texts in secondary education: a review of intervention studies. <i>Journal of Writing Research</i>, 10(vol. 10 issue 3), 401–428. https://doi.org/10.17239/jowr-2019.10.03.01</p>	<p>16 (quasi-) experimental studies (synthesis and source-based writing; upper elementary to higher education; only experimental and quasi-experimental designs included, drawing on post-test comparisons) The review findings are based mainly on 6 studies which were qualitatively analysed in order to identify key design principles.</p>	<p>Studies with an average effect size of .80 were included in review, but this is not the average effect size across studies (this was not calculated/ provided)</p>	<p>The review focuses on synthesis writing tasks, i.e. tasks that involve writing about information gleaned from reading a variety of sources on a given topic.</p>	<p>6th grade to undergraduate level</p>	<p>Studies (n=6) with an effect size of .80 or greater were selected and analysed to identify successful instructional practices for synthesis writing. This expert analysis was done across three phases including Dutch/Flemish writing proficiency researchers, teacher education students and finally international writing proficiency researchers. Based on this analysis, the following principles are proposed: 1) Students need to be <u>taught</u> the processes involved in <i>selecting, organising and connecting</i> information from across sources.; 2) <i>Selecting information</i>: students must be taught to fully comprehend individual sources. They should engage in activities that encourage evaluation of these sources (e.g. through questioning, comparing/contrasting sources, examining source information); 3) <i>Organising information</i>: Students should learn how to compare source <i>features</i> by, for example, examining authorial information; they should also learn how to analyse <i>source content</i>, by for example comparing information from sources using graphic organisers; 4) <i>Connecting information</i>: students should be taught how to write coherent texts based on the selection and organisation of information, through, for example, comparing and contrasting the organisation of sample/mentor texts; 5) Students should be in a position to adapt the strategies they are taught for synthesis writing to suit their own needs/preferences.</p>

<p>Weiss, K.A., McDermott, M.A., & Hand, B. Characterising immersive argument-based inquiry learning environments in school-based education: a systematic literature review. <i>Studies in Science Education</i>, volume/issue no. not yet available. DOI: 10.1080/03057267.2021.1897931</p>	<p>2013 onwards; 39 articles based on 16 immersive ABI approaches</p>	<p>Not analysed/ provided</p>	<p>Argument-based inquiry in science (as distinct from structured and socio-scientific approaches to argument)</p>	<p>Primary and secondary grades</p>	<p>This study provides a synthesis of the key features of instruction associated with immersive argument-based inquiry, an approach to argumentation that emphasises the <i>process</i> of argumentation within <i>inquiry</i> based approaches. Key features included: Student actions: Direct student involvement in argumentation; Small group work; Discussion; Investigation; Share/present ideas; Justify with evidence; Focus on understanding of science concepts Teacher actions: Encourage argumentation; student knowledge generation; Provide resources; Asking questions; Sharing authority; Communicate scientific norms (e.g. through modelling); Model dialogue/language use; Emphasise important ideas Generative opportunities (opportunities to generate scientific knowledge): Student authorship of initial activity (e.g. in generating inquiry questions); Student-designed investigation procedures Authors provide a continuum of less and more generative approaches, i.e. approaches that give students less and more control over the direction of inquiry and generation of knowledge</p>
<p>Wissinger, D. R., & Ciullo, S. (2018). Historical Literacy Research for Students with and at Risk for Learning Disabilities: A Systematic Review. <i>Learning Disabilities Research & Practice</i>, 33(4), 237–249.</p>	<p>12 quantitative studies published between 2000-2017</p>	<p>Overall effect size not provided; moderate to large effect sizes observed across 12 studies</p>	<p>How students with LD (learning disabilities') as supported with historical literacy</p>	<p>Students with or at risk of LD in grades 4-12</p>	<p>Historical literacy interventions are defined as instruction that “targets the skills required to read, reason, write, and learn with historical evidence such as source documents, artifacts, photographs, movies, and artwork” (p.237). Studies on disciplinary reading in history support the use of collaborative instruction and historical-strategy instruction. Cognitive apprenticeship models are supported for historical writing, as well as the use of schemes and critical questions. Project-based inquiry also finds support.</p>
<p>Wright, K., Franks, A., Kuo, L.-J., McTigue, E., & Serrano, J. (2016). Both Theory and Practice: Science Literacy Instruction and Theories of Reading. <i>International Journal of Science & Mathematics</i></p>	<p>22 articles published in the Journal of Adolescent and Adult Literacy between 2004-2015</p>				<p>Review revealed that in science literacy, vocabulary instructional practices are frequently supported with Schema and Dual-Coding theories. Articles also frequently used theories grounded in social dynamics, including social constructionism and sociocultural perspective, to support literacy instruction. However, recommendations for other aspects of instructional practices in science literacy are generally not well-grounded in major reading theories. Over the past decade there has been a shift from content-area literacy skills, which involves the instruction of literacy strategies common in</p>

<p><i>Education</i>, 14(7), 1275–1292. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-015-9661-2</p>					<p>multiple contexts, to disciplinary literacy, focussing on the skills required for reading and writing in a specific field, such as science. Background knowledge and vocabulary development predominate as instructional approaches. However the need to move away from fact-focussed instruction in science towards minds-on hands-on activity is stressed. Teachers’ knowledge of the theories underpinning instructional practices is important and should be made more explicit in research studies.</p>
<p>Yang, X., Kuo, L.-J., & Jiang, L. (2020). Connecting Theory and Practice: A Systematic Review of K-5 Science and Math Literacy Instruction. <i>International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education</i>, 18(2), 203–219.</p>	<p>59 articles published in <i>The Reading Teacher</i> between 2006-2016</p>				<p>Systematic review of articles published in <i>The Reading Teacher</i> that aims to examine the connection between theory and practice for K-5 science and maths literacy instruction. Findings revealed that most of the science and maths literacy practices were aligned with social theories, including social constructionism and socio-cultural perspectives. However, the authors revealed gaps between theory and practice and suggest a strengthening of the connection between theory and practice underpinned by joint efforts of researchers and practitioners alike. Reading comprehension, vocabulary and writing were the three primary literacy skills addressed by K-5 teachers. Analysis suggested that approaches used by teachers included using multiple reading materials, incorporating reading and writing strategies, close reading, comprehension strategy instruction, rereading, shared reading, visuals, technologies and strategies to support English Language Learners.</p>